

Lived Experiences of Secondary Public School Heads in Managing Schools Under The DepEd Management Framework

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the lived experiences of secondary public-school heads in managing schools under the DepEd Management Framework. The results of this study served as a basis for a development plan for secondary public-school heads. The study was conducted in both districts in Lopez, Quezon: Lopez East District and Lopez West District. It utilized a qualitative research design, which aimed to describe, understand, and interpret the meaning of the participants' experiences in managing schools under the DepEd Management Framework. The researcher conducted structured interviews with the participants. The formulated meanings and themes, based on the dominant responses of the participants, included the following: The primary challenge experienced in managing schools, teachers, and stakeholders was balancing multiple responsibilities in both personal and professional domains. The managerial skills applied by school heads included leadership, administrative, instructional leadership, and interpersonal skills. Various seminars, training sessions, and workshops were

offered to school heads to strengthen their managerial competencies. The proposed development plan was recommended to be implemented year-round among other secondary public-school heads in both Lopez East District and Lopez West District in the municipality of Lopez, Quezon. The researcher recommended that school heads continue seeking professional advancement in managerial skills, including administrative skills, instructional leadership, and interpersonal skills. School heads were advised to continue attending training sessions that would improve their knowledge, skills, and mastery in managing schools, teachers, students, and stakeholders. School heads were urged to continue strengthening partnerships with various stakeholders, including parents, the Local Government Unit, and other public and private entities. The proposed development plan was recommended for implementation, with the suggestion to seek guidance and support from higher authorities to ensure the continued involvement of all secondary school heads in Lopez, Quezon.

Keywords: *challenges, development plan, experiences, managerial skills, opportunities*

Introduction

A nation's quality is largely determined by its educational system, which aims to produce competent citizens who can compete on a global scale, take responsibility for their actions, and look ahead.

It should rise as a result of the presence of schools, which are educational institutions established to produce more educated human resources (Hartati, Pepriyeni, & Suryana, 2020).

Education is essential for a civilization's ability to adapt to its environment. This cannot happen without well-educated individuals leading the way. Individuals in a society must acquire and apply new skills and information to conserve, share, and develop their common cultural heritage and the current level of social and scientific knowledge. Thus, school leaders have a significant impact on the effectiveness of schools.

As stated in DepEd Order No. 024, series 2020, the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH) represent the core regulations for school leaders within the Philippine Department of Education (DepEd). This framework highlights the dual role of school leaders as administrators and instructional guides, outlining their duties across five essential areas: strategic leadership, overseeing school resources and operations, prioritizing teaching and learning, fostering professional and personal growth, and cultivating relationships. Every domain aims to increase school leaders' ability to effectively handle the challenges of educational administration.

In the first domain, "Leading Strategically," school leaders are expected to understand and implement relevant laws and regulations that align with research studies in schools. For effective policy formulation and implementation, the latter is particularly pertinent in respect to education design. The second domain focuses on "Managing School Operations and Resources," focuses on the efficient use of resources by school leaders to facilitate learning. Research has shown that faculty and staff remain committed when the school leadership is transparent in financial matters.

The third domain, "Focusing on Teaching and Learning," underlines the demand for school leaders to promote and support teacher professional growth. The school administration can promote better learning outcomes by giving teachers opportunities to try innovative teaching approaches. School leaders are encouraged to develop their subordinates and themselves in the fourth domain, "Developing Self and Others." The fifth domain is called "Building Connections" and focuses on the need to establish strong relationships with stakeholders such as parents. Fostering a positive educational ecosystem requires this kind of collaboration.

The policies of PPSSH provide a strong foundation for school managers to operate their institutions efficiently and foster a culture of excellence. School leaders can address challenges and issues in their work environments effectively with these standards.

The education management framework serves as a useful standard, and management has a significant impact on the quality of education. The aims and policies implemented by education management are erroneous, which leads to a number of issues in the field (Pasaribu, 2021). Research in this area is required to address a number of issues and ensure that education is high-quality and important to people's lives.

According to Nur (2020), the school head is a functional teacher who oversees the school where the teaching and learning process takes place and the interactions between teachers and students. However, Article 12, Paragraph 1 of Government Regulation Number 28 of 1990 concerning Basic Education states: "School principals are responsible for the implementation of educational activities, school management, development of other educational staff, as well as the use and maintenance of facilities. and infrastructure." Since education management requires good and quality human resources, the school head is directly in charge of managing education management in schools.

The leadership of school heads has a significant impact on fostering a positive and cooperative work environment and relationships among the human resources in the immediate vicinity. Therefore, to

create efficient educational administration and accomplish educational goals, school heads' professional knowledge, competencies, and leadership qualities are crucial.

Deciding to lead a school will always require careful consideration and judgment. Although the advantages, rewards, power, and authority are alluring, the duties and responsibilities force one to pause and consider one's options. The shift from classroom instruction to administrative leadership is becoming increasingly difficult as school heads are held to higher standards by accountability metrics.

Three processes make up school leadership: (a) creating an organization's vision and using it to guide activities; (b) communicating effectively to align people with the organization's vision; and (c) inspiring and motivating staff to take action in the face of obstacles. Organizational change is influenced by the processes that comprise leadership (Merle, 2022).

The ability of school heads to plan, organize, coordinate, regulate, and guide an organization's operations to achieve predetermined goals and objectives is referred to as managerial skills (Suyatno & Santosa, 2022). Another way to describe managerial skills is as specific knowledge necessary for school heads to carry out their roles and responsibilities efficiently to meet educational objectives. School head's unique ability to run the schools is known as their managerial skills, often attained through training and experience. Another way we can define managerial skills is as a collection of actions that result in efficient work performance; without this, school head knowledge is frequently meaningless.

Leadership abilities strengthened the school's progress and efficacy. School heads guide their constituents toward excellence and provide high-quality education, acting as the ship's captains. A school head's leadership greatly aids in identifying the school's predetermined goals and encapsulating them via the creation and execution of the School Improvement Plan (SIP). Regardless of the school they are assigned to, they make sure to invest their time and energy in meeting the demands of the institution and offering the most resources to enhance the teaching-learning process.

According to Lamas (2021), school performance is a problem that affects children, parents, teachers, and authorities in practically every country in the world. Leading and running the school is a real challenge, particularly in rural areas where the obstacles are severe. Schools in rural areas have a lack of physical and human resources due to their remote location (Tejada & Chieng, 2024). School heads and teachers in a distant area of Bhutan faced difficulties when it came to teaching. These challenges included issues with the school heads and teachers, education issues, and the environment. Similarly, Indonesia faces significant educational challenges, particularly in schools situated in remote areas. As a result, educational administrators faced significant challenges while administering schools across regional borders.

Meanwhile, Pakistan, as a developing country, lacks numerous civic amenities. Due to the large number of children needing basic education, remote areas continue to exist despite insufficient fundamental amenities. But for schools in remote areas, the government makes sure to address their educational issue. Basic education is made possible despite the low resources available (Deema, 2021).

The current state of basic education in the Philippines constantly worries the Department of Education (DepEd). Numerous changes have been implemented to enhance the caliber of education, but based on observations, the situations are nearly the same. In the study of Directo & Damaco (2020), the Schools Division of La Union, remote areas school teachers and school heads are living examples of their critical role in helping individuals who are most in need of educational services. However, they disclosed that they had both satisfying and discouraging experiences that tested their dedication, particularly in providing high-quality instruction. It is extremely difficult for teachers and school heads to be allocated to physically remote areas with a clear lack of resources. To guarantee that students have access to the

resources and education they are entitled to, teachers and school heads implement a variety of plans and initiatives.

Lopez, Quezon, is considered geographically isolated, far from the cities or urban areas. Some schools don't have a signal or internet connection, and teachers and school heads are hard to contact if there are urgent reports that need to be complied with and submitted. That's why the researcher noticed that most school heads in Lopez, Quezon, assigned in remote areas are new and young; they are blessed to handle a school at a young age, but with greater responsibility. Conflict arises, especially today, as the Department of Education has had a lot of management changes.

The researcher, who is both an educator and aspiring school head, aimed to know the challenges experienced, the managerial skills school heads possess to cope with, and the opportunities given to the public secondary school heads in managing schools under the Department of Education management framework as the basis for the development of a development plan for secondary school heads that can be used by the newly appointed public school head and also can benchmark by other school heads from other district and municipalities.

Objective of the Study

The study determines the lived experiences of secondary public-school heads in Lopez, Quezon, in managing schools under the DepEd management framework. Lived experiences focused on the challenges, managerial strategies, and opportunities given by the DepEd. The study provided a proposed developmental plan that will serve as their guide in managing public schools in the Department of Education.

Statement of the Problem

The study was focused on the experiences of public secondary school heads in managing schools under the Department of Education Management framework as the basis for the development of the development plan.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the most significant experience of public secondary school heads in managing the schools, as regards their challenges encountered, managerial abilities applied, and opportunities under the Department of Education management framework?
2. Based on the testimonies of the participants, what meanings can be derived?
3. What themes emerged from the meanings derived from the participants' testimonies?
4. Based on the results, what development plan can be developed to improve the managerial skills of public secondary school heads?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research design, specifically utilizing phenomenology to explore the lived experiences of public secondary school heads in Lopez, Quezon. This approach enabled an in-depth examination of the participants' narratives, focusing on the challenges they encountered, the managerial strategies they applied, and the opportunities provided to them under the Department of Education management framework. Phenomenology seeks to uncover the essence and meaning of lived experiences from the perspectives of those who experienced the phenomenon. Rooted in the philosophical

traditions of Edmund Husserl and expanded by Martin Heidegger, it emphasizes understanding human experiences by setting aside biases—a practice known as bracketing (Maree, 2020). This method provides a detailed account of how individuals make sense of specific life experiences (Denzin & Lincoln, 2021).

Selection of Participants

Eight (8) secondary public-school heads in Lopez, Quezon, both Lopez East and Lopez West Districts, under the Division Office of Quezon Province, were considered as subjects of the study.

For the qualitative phase, these eight heads of secondary public schools were chosen using simple random sampling. Simple random sampling was selected because it ensured that the sample was representative of the entire population and minimized selection bias by giving each member of the population an equal chance of being included in the sample. The eight participants in the qualitative study were five school heads from the Lopez West District and three from the Lopez East District. In qualitative research, this technique was instrumental in trying to reach populations difficult to sample due to a limited number of participants possessing the required characteristics.

In order to gain a thorough grasp of secondary public school heads' experiences in managing the schools under the DepEd Framework, it was necessary to make sure that the qualitative data gathered was perceptive and comprehensive. This strategy was warranted since it made it possible to choose participants who might have provided insightful viewpoints and subtle details that interviews alone might not have been able to obtain.

Validation of Instrument

When assessing the validity of the semi-structured interview guide questions, the researcher consulted the experts and requested their feedback and suggestions on the instrument. Each of their suggestions was utilized to help finalize the research instruments. The researcher asked an assistant of three (3) elementary school principals of Lopez East District and Lopez West District, since there were only nineteen (19) secondary school heads in Lopez, Quezon, and eight (8) of them became the participants of the study.

To ensure that the validators were specialists in the same field, the researcher considered their similar circumstances, allowing them to support one another's point of view. That is why three (3) school heads with high positions in elementary from both East and West Districts served as validators of the guide questions to obtain better knowledge.

The researcher personally visited the three (3) elementary school principals in their respective schools to formally ask permission as well to validate the research interview guide questions, explained the purpose and goal of and study to have background knowledge on the paper, and gave the research interview guide.

After the consultation, the three (3) elementary school principals all submitted their suggestions and recommendations, and the researcher secured a certificate of validation.

Data Generation

Prior to the commencement of data collection, a formal request for permission to conduct the study was submitted to the Schools Division Office in Lopez, Quezon. Upon receiving approval, the researcher proceeded with the data collection process as outlined in the subsequent sections.

Semi-structured interviews were two-way conversations in which the interviewer asked participants questions to gather data and gain insight into their thoughts, beliefs, perspectives, opinions, and behaviors. To obtain the necessary information and determine the challenges, managerial strategies they applied, and the opportunities given to the public-school heads, semi-structured interviews were conducted with eight (8) secondary public-school heads in Lopez, Quezon. It was from a representative subset of the population that generalizations about the entire population could be formed, and from this subset, the population as a whole could be inferred.

Eight (8) public secondary school heads participated in semi-structured interviews. During the process, the researcher employed interview guidelines. The interview questions for all participants were nearly identical, except for a few questions based on the participants' responses or follow-up questions. The interview questions were formulated according to the study's objectives and the research questions. To ensure a comprehensive understanding of the participants' responses, the researcher probed and sought clarifications throughout the interview sessions.

Data saturation was reached after conducting in-depth, semi-structured interviews with eight (8) secondary public-school heads in Lopez, Quezon. The participants were selected from two districts to ensure diversity of perspectives and contexts.

During the sixth interview, recurring themes and similar responses started to emerge concerning the participants' challenges, strategies, and insights in managing schools under the DepEd Management Framework. The following interviews, especially the seventh and eighth, did not bring up any new themes, ideas, or information; instead, they confirmed the categories that had already been found.

Qualitative Data Analysis

To get an overall feel for the material, the researcher studied the data and noted its significance. Additional categories and sub-categories were established, and each piece of data presented was categorized to gain a rough understanding of what it meant. Colaizzi's seven-step procedure for analyzing and interpreting qualitative data was followed in this investigation.

Colaizzi's method of researching the management of schools within the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines provided a structured approach to understanding the lived experiences of school heads and their challenges. Colaizzi's phenomenological method consisted of seven distinct steps that facilitated a deep exploration of participants' experiences, making it particularly suitable for qualitative research in educational settings. The first step involved familiarization with the data, where researchers immersed themselves in the accounts of school heads to grasp the overall context of their experiences. This was followed by identifying significant statements that directly related to the phenomenon under investigation, the management practices, and the challenges faced by school leaders.

Next, researchers formulated meanings from these significant statements, ensuring they remained objective and set aside personal biases. This was crucial in educational research, as it allowed for an authentic representation of school heads' experiences. The identified meanings were then clustered into themes that emerged across different accounts, providing insight into common challenges such as resource allocation, community engagement, and professional development needs. Following this thematic analysis, an exhaustive description of the phenomenon was developed, integrating all themes into a comprehensive narrative that encapsulated the essence of school management experiences.

The fifth step involved condensing this exhaustive description into a fundamental structure that highlighted essential aspects of the phenomenon. Finally, Colaizzi's method emphasized validation by returning to participants to ensure that the findings accurately reflected their experiences. This iterative process not only enhanced the credibility of the research but also fostered a sense of ownership among

school heads regarding the insights derived from their narratives. Overall, employing Colaizzi's method in this context allowed for a nuanced understanding of how school heads navigated their roles within DepEd, ultimately contributing valuable knowledge that could inform policy and practice in educational leadership.

Thematic Reflection

Interpretative philosophy was often used in qualitative data analysis (QDA), which Maree (2020) claimed was focused on the meaningful and symbolic content of qualitative data. Specifically, in this research, qualitative data were analyzed to make sense of the participants' challenges, the managerial strategies applied, and the opportunities provided by the Department of Education management framework to the public secondary school heads in Lopez, Quezon.

The findings were based on the participants' views, values, experiences, and emotions. Thematic data analysis was employed in this research. By using thematic data analysis, the researcher was able to produce a comprehensive and complete description of the data since it was a very flexible method that could be adapted to the objectives of the study.

The research participants' views were examined using theme analysis to identify commonalities and contrasts, as well as to provide unexpected discoveries, as shown by King (2021) and Braun (Braun & Clarke, 2020). While theme analysis was an effective tool for uncovering commonalities and discrepancies among the views of various study participants, it was also shown to provide surprising results, according to King (2021), Braun (2020), and Clarke (2020). The participant's information was transcribed and organized by the researcher. This was done by repeatedly reviewing and listening to the recordings of the interviews that had been conducted.

The researcher's notes gathered verbatim during the interviews were used to enhance the procedure. This was repeated to have a better grasp of the data. Doing so provided the researcher with a sense of what the transcripts' themes were. It was also possible to identify certain themes based on the first coding terms from the interviewees. Afterward, the interviews were analyzed and coded. The researcher used a highlighter or keypad to categorize the interviews based on pertinent terms, phrases, and sentences. It was customary to start with coding the first interview. New coding words were inevitably devised in response to emerging trends to accurately comprehend the responses.

Literature Comparison

Colaizzi was often used in qualitative data analysis, which Maree (2020) claimed focused on the meaningful and symbolic content of qualitative data. Additionally, Colaizzi's seven-step process was adapted and applied to the data analysis. Iterative refining was used to make sure that no aspect of the phenomenon was missed. After the initial interview was transcribed, data analysis began. A committee of professionals discussed the findings to ensure the data was properly analyzed and interpreted (Finlayson, 2021).

In comparison, in this study, qualitative data were analyzed to make sense of the challenges the participants encountered, the managerial abilities they possessed, and the opportunities they had in managing schools under the Department of Education's management framework. The researcher personally followed the steps to secure the validity of the data.

Colaizzi created his descriptive phenomenology approach (Colaizzi, 1978, as cited in Edward & Welch, 2021) "under the supervision of Giorgi, who produced a body of literature devoted to the ongoing articulation and demonstration of empirically based phenomenological research in psychology." As part of Colaizzi's procedural modification of Giorgi's method of investigation, the results were validated with volunteers. The transcript analysis had to be sent back to the individual participants for their consideration

as part of this procedure. Participant clarification and/or elaboration required the inclusion of additional material in the final explanation of the findings.

Similarly, in this study, Colaizzi's seven steps were applied to secure the significant experiences of public secondary school heads regarding challenges experienced, managerial strategies applied to cope with these challenges, and the opportunities given in managing schools under the Department of Education management framework in Lopez, Quezon.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Most Significant Experiences of Secondary Public School Heads in Lopez, Quezon, in managing schools

Lived Experiences	Summary of Findings
Challenges	The major challenges faced by the secondary public school heads in Lopez, Quezon, are managing the schools, teachers, and stakeholders while balancing multiple responsibilities, including personal and work matters.
Managerial Abilities	The managerial abilities/Skills applied by the secondary public school heads in managing schools, teachers, and stakeholders' experiences, knowledge, and training about leadership, administrative, interpersonal, and instructional leadership skills.
Opportunities	The opportunities given by the Department of Education to secondary public school heads in Lopez, Quezon are numerous seminars, training, and workshops about leadership and management.

Table 2. Formulated Meanings and Themes based on the testimonies of Secondary Public School Heads of Lopez, Quezon.

	Meanings	Themes
Challenges	The major challenges faced by the secondary public school heads in handling school points out a specific variable in decision-making and balancing multiple responsibilities. It requires balancing multiple responsibilities, including managing teachers and stakeholders, handling finances, ensuring academic excellence, and maintaining discipline.	Balancing Multiple Responsibilities
Managerial Skills	The dominant responses of secondary school heads in	Decision Making and Communication

	managerial skills applied to solve problems efficiently, a continuous learning process, school success and continuous improvement, decision making, having a positive learning environment, and having open, good, respectful, and transparent communication with the teachers is vital to maintaining a strong relationship between teachers, stakeholders, and the school head.	
Opportunities	Secondary public school heads have the privilege of having numerous seminars, training, and workshops conducted by the Department of Education and other private sectors. Awards and recognition are also given to public school heads to recognize the skills, knowledge, and abilities they have contributed.	Numerous seminars, training, and workshops

Table 3. Output of the Study

Project Name	Brief Discussion
Project ARRA	The proposed developmental plan, named Project ARRA, which stands for Acaylar's Reinforcing Relationship and Advancement, is very timely since our department places emphasis on the importance of technical assistance not only to the public secondary school heads but also to all the public school heads, regardless of whether they are assigned to elementary or secondary schools, and also to the teachers and inspiring school heads, and wants to focus on increasing abilities in terms of administrative skills and instructional leadership.

The tables above are summarized findings of this study based on the four research questions outlined in the Statement of the Problem (SOP). These findings highlight the lived experiences, meanings, themes, and proposed development plan derived from the participants' testimonies.

Summary of Findings

1. On the Most Significant Experiences of Secondary Public School Heads in Lopez, Quezon

The significant experiences of secondary public school heads in Lopez, Quezon, include managing the schools, teachers, and stakeholders while balancing multiple responsibilities, including personal and work matters. Also, school heads apply managerial skills in managing schools, teachers, and stakeholders, including leadership, administrative, interpersonal, and instructional leadership skills. The opportunities given by the Department of Education include numerous seminars, training, and workshops about leadership and management.

2. On Problems 2 and 3, the Formulated Meanings and Themes based on the testimonies of Secondary Public School Heads of Lopez, Quezon, in terms of:
 - 1.1. Challenges experienced by public secondary school heads in managing the schools, teachers, and stakeholders.

Results showed that the challenges faced by the secondary public school heads in handling school points out a specific variable in decision-making and balancing multiple responsibilities. It requires balancing multiple responsibilities, including managing teachers and stakeholders, handling finances, ensuring academic excellence, and maintaining discipline. School heads need to navigate the actual school processes and align their decisions with the existing issuances of DepEd.

- 1.2. Managerial Skills are applied by public secondary school heads when managing the schools.

The dominant responses of secondary school heads in managerial skills applied to solve problems efficiently, a continuous learning process, school success and continuous improvement, decision making, and having a positive learning environment. In addition, open, good, respectful, and transparent communication with the teachers is vital to maintaining a strong relationship between teachers, stakeholders, and the school head. Having a positive, supportive, and effective learning environment, working together effectively, and achieving goals indicate that school heads' leadership becomes successful.

- 1.3. Opportunities are given to public secondary school heads to manage the schools.

The result showed that school heads are allowed to have numerous seminars, training, and workshops conducted by the Department of Education and other private sectors. Also, awards are given to secondary public school heads to recognize the skills, knowledge, and abilities they have contributed. In addition, some also shared other recognition and empowerment, such as incentives and opportunities in professional development, the privilege to implement school policies and achievements, and acknowledgment from others.

3. The Proposed Development Plan can be developed for the secondary public school heads of Lopez, Quezon.

With the findings of the study, the researcher proposed the implementation of the Development Plan entitled Project ARRA stands for Acaylar's Reinforcing, Relationship and Advancement. This project's major objective is to promote the ties between all secondary school heads in the municipality of Lopez, Quezon, and both Lopez East and Lopez West Districts further.

Conclusions

Based on the findings gathered, the following conclusions were drawn.

1. The most significant experience of secondary public school heads in the challenges encountered is balancing the multiple responsibilities of school heads in their work and personal lives. Leadership skills and abilities are important managerial skills needed of school heads in managing schools, teachers, and stakeholders. Numerous seminars, training, and workshops are the opportunities given to all school heads by the Department of Education.
2. The formulated meaning and themes based on the dominant responses of the participants are:
 - 2.1. The challenging experience in managing the schools, teachers, and stakeholders is balancing the multiple responsibilities, personal and work.
 - 2.2. Leadership, administrative, instructional leadership, and interpersonal skills are the managerial skills applied.
 - 2.3. Different seminars, training, and workshops are given to all school heads.
3. The proposed Development Plan should be implemented year-round among other secondary public school heads in the municipality of Lopez, Quezon.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn by the researcher, the following recommendations were made.

For DepEd Administrators:

1. Provide continuous leadership and management training to school heads to enhance their competence in implementing the DepEd Management Framework.
2. Ensure timely provision of resources, budget allocation, and technical assistance to support school operations.
3. Review and strengthen policies to address the unique challenges faced by schools in various contexts.

For Teachers:

4. Actively participate in school planning, decision-making, and implementation of programs aligned with the DepEd Management Framework.
5. Engage in professional development activities to improve teaching strategies and student outcomes.
6. Maintain strong collaboration with school heads to achieve institutional goals.

For Stakeholders (Parents, LGUs, and Community Partners):

7. Strengthen partnerships with the school through resource sharing, infrastructure support, and participation in school programs.
8. Advocate for educational initiatives that prioritize learner welfare and holistic development.
9. Actively engage in school-community activities that foster a positive and supportive learning environment.

For Public Secondary School Heads:

10. The school heads must continue seeking professional advancement in terms of managerial abilities and skills such as administrative skills, instructional leadership, and interpersonal skills.
11. The school heads must continue attending training, seminars, and workshops that will improve their knowledge, skills, and mastery of managing schools, teachers, students, and stakeholders.

12. School heads must continue strengthening partnerships with different stakeholders like parents, the Local Government Unit, and other public and private stakeholders.
13. Implement the Proposed Development Plan and seek help and advice to a higher position to continue the programs for secondary public school heads in Lopez, Quezon.

For Future Researchers:

14. Conduct similar studies in other regions to compare and contrast the lived experiences of school heads across diverse contexts.
15. Explore other dimensions of the DepEd Management Framework, such as its impact on student performance and teacher retention.
16. Use a larger sample size or mixed-methods design to provide more comprehensive findings and validate results.

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